

Documentation of Sensor Data Correction Script

SAIL

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Revision History

Date	Author	Description of change
2020-12-02	S. Barbosa	First Draft
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1 Introduction

The data gathered from the systems sensors could contain reading errors. To overcome this issue, a program (hereafter designated parser) was developed in C language and is executed for all the files by means of a bash script. The script and the parser are described in section 2.1 and 2.2 respectively.

The expected file tree is shown in Figure 1.

```

./
├── 01_efield_cr1000
├── 02_efield_cr1000
├── 05_gamma_naitl
├── 06_cic
├── 07_visibility_sws050
├── sail_generate.sh
├── sail_parser
└── towfish
  
```

Figure 1: Sensor data file tree

The folders with names started by numbers and the towfish folder contain the data coming directly from the onboard storage system. The data is organized by date and hour. Each day has an associated folder named YYYYMMDD where YYYY is the year, MM the month and DD the day. All data related to, i.e. 10th January 2020 and from Electric Field 1 sensor (E1), are placed in a folder named 20200110, inside the 01efiled.cr1000 directory. Inside this folder are the files for each hour (from 00 to 23) respecting the following structure:

$$SS_YYYYMMDD_HH.txt$$

where SS is the sensor identification, YYYY is the year, MM the month, DD the day and HH the hour. Considering the previous example, the data from 02:00:00 until 02:59:59, are placed in the file E1_20200110_02.txt.

Folders with names started by “SAIL_SD_“ were created to contain the final data with XX denoting the sensor field.

The sensor field could be one of the following presented in Table 1 (Sensor ID).

2 Sensor data parsing system

The sensor data parsing system is composed of two applications: a parser and a script. The parser is an application that reads a single log file and generates the same data file without log errors if any. The script will

Sensor	Sensor ID
Electric field 1	E1
Electric field 2	E2
Gamma	GA
Visibility	VI
Solar radiance	SL
Towfish CTD	CTD

Table 1: List of sensors available and their correspondent ID

be responsible for calling the parser in a consecutive manner for each sensor/hour for a complete day.

2.1 The script

The usage of the bash script in a terminal is as follows:

```
>> ./sail_generate.sh [sensor] [initial date] [final date]
```

The sensor parameter is the same as the ones presented in the Table 1 or the ID ALL can be used to parse all the sensors for the dates provided. The initial and final dates must be in the format YYYYMMDD. For example, if we desire to generate the files related to the Electric Field 1 sensor for the dates from 5th January 2020 until 27th February 2020, we should execute the script with the following arguments:

```
>> ./sail_generate.sh E1 20200105 20200227
```

The bash script starts to verify the number of input parameters (arguments). If this number is less than 3 (sensor, initial date and final date), an error message is displayed with the correct usage and the script is aborted. Output example:

```
>> Wrong number of parameters or invalid input data
>> Usage:
>> ./sail_generate (sensor) (initial date) (final date)
>> Available options for sensor: [E1, E2, GA, VI, SL, CTD or ALL].
>> Date format: YYYYMMDD
```

If the number of arguments is valid, the script executes different functions according to the selected sensor (Figure 2). Figure 3 (Sensor process flowchart) details the processing for each specific sensor SS (process_SS() in flowchart illustrated in Figure 2). Based on the initial and final dates, all the files located in the sensor folder (starting by a number) which are within the specified time interval are processed.

The first step is to unpack the original log file to be processed. Then, it is created a sub-folder, inside the output sensor folder (SAIL_SD_SS), with name YYYYMMDD. Then, from 0 until 23, it is generated the path that will be used as input for the parser program.

For example, to process the data of the visibility sensor from 10th January 2020, from 15:00:00 to 15:59:59, the script executes the parser as follows:

```
>>./sail_parser/sail_parser VI  
"$PWD/07_visibility_sws050/20200110/VI_20200110.15.txt"  
"$PWD/SAIL_SD_VI/20200110/20200110.15.txt"
```

(The \$PWD macro returns the path for the current working directory).

After this step, the number of files that are inside the final destination folder is determined. If this number is greater than 0, the folder (corresponding to one day) is compressed. Then, it is removed. This step is for compressing only folders with contents avoiding the presence of empty folders at the end of the process.

2.2 The parser

The parser is an application developed in C. It has as input parameter the sensor identification (See table 1), the path for the input file and the path for the output file. As the first step, the program tries to open the file with the original data as well as the output file. If unsuccessful, a message with usage instructions is displayed and the program execution is aborted. With access to the raw data file, line by line is read and, based on the selected type of sensor, the number of expected fields is confirmed. If the number of collected fields matches the number of expected fields, the line is considered as valid. In this situation, it is added to the final output file. If not, the line is neglected and an error message is displayed. The number of expected fields for each sensor is pre-defined according to Table 2.

At the end, both opened files (input and output files) are closed and the program finishes. The flowchart of the parser application is illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 2: Script flowchart

Figure 3: Sensor process flowchart

Sensor	Expected number of fields
Electric field 1	17
Electric field 2	15
Gamma	9
Visibility	16
Solar radiance	17
CTD	12

Table 2: Expected number of fields for each sensor

Figure 4: Parser flowchart